

INCREASING THE NUMBER OF BOUTIQUE HOTEL IN UZBEKISTAN AND GENERAL RECOMMENDATION FOR IMPROVING THEIR QUALITY OF DESIGN.

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Abstract.

This article investigates the possible benefits of increasing the number of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan, with an emphasis on enhancing their design quality in order to provide guests with a unique cultural experience. Using examples from European countries such as France, the research claims that boutique hotels might provide a more customized and authentic vacation experience than larger chain hotels and offers broad tips for improving the quality of design in boutique hotels, such as using local cultural features and materials and creating a feeling of place that reflects the surrounding area. These findings highlight some of the key appeals of boutique hotels – their stylish and vintage decor reflecting local culture, intimate ambiance, and ability to provide a unique perspective into Uzbek lifestyle. The discussion is based on the idea that expanding the quantity of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan may boost tourism and economic growth while simultaneously maintaining and honouring the country's unique cultural legacy.

Keywords.

Boutique hotels, design and quality, numbers of boutique hotels, culture, unique atmosphere, art, traditional materials, tourist, history of a country, architecture

1. INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's boutique hotel scene is blossoming. In recent years, the country has seen a surge of stylish and intimate boutique properties opening in popular tourist destinations like Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva. Once a land

dominated by large resorts and hotel chains, Uzbekistan is now welcoming more independent hotels that aim to reflect the nation's unique cultural heritage and spirit. The rise of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan signals the country's growing appeal as a sophisticated travel destination. As more visitors' flock to Uzbekistan to experience its historic Silk Road cities, lush landscapes, and colourful bazaars, there is demand for lodgings that offer both luxury and authenticity. Boutique hotels fit the bill by providing upscale amenities and design while also integrating traditional Uzbek crafts, textiles, and architectural details.

1.1 HISTORY

Boutique hotels are a relatively new concept in the hospitality industry, emerging in the 1980s as a response to the cookie-cutter approach of larger chain hotels. The term "boutique hotel" was first coined by ¹¹⁸Steve Rubell, co-owner of the iconic Studio 54 nightclub in New York City, to describe the Morgans Hotel, which he and his partner ¹¹⁹Ian Schrager opened in 1984. The Morgans Hotel was designed to be a more intimate and personalized alternative to the large, impersonal hotels that dominated the industry at the time. The hotel featured unique design elements, such as custom-made furniture and artwork. The success of the Morgans Hotel inspired other hospitality entrepreneurs to create their own boutique hotels, and the concept quickly spread around the world. By the 1990s, boutique hotels had become a popular trend in the hospitality industry, with hotels such as the Blakes Hotel in London and the Royalton Hotel in New York City leading the way.

Picture 1

Morgans hotel in NEW YORK: world's first boutique hotel

¹¹⁸ American Entrepreneur and Co-owner of the New York city Disco Studio 54

¹¹⁹Hotelier and real estate developer, credited for co-creating the "boutique hotel" category of accommodation

1.2 LEGISLATION

The tourism industry in Uzbekistan is governed by a range of laws and regulations, aimed at promoting sustainable tourism and protecting the country's cultural heritage. Here are some key pieces of legislation that apply to the tourism industry in Uzbekistan:

1.2.1

The "Tourism Development Concept" (2018) sets out the government's strategy for developing the tourism industry in Uzbekistan. The concept includes provisions for the development of tourism infrastructure, the promotion of sustainable tourism practices, and the protection and preservation of cultural heritage sites.

1.2.2

The "Law on Tourism" (2019) regulates the tourism industry in Uzbekistan and sets out the rights and obligations of tourism businesses and tourists. The law covers issues such as licensing, taxation, and safety standards for tourism businesses, as well as the rights and responsibilities of tourists visiting Uzbekistan.

1.2.3

The "Law on Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship" (2019) provides support for small and medium-sized enterprises, including those in the tourism industry. The law offers a range of incentives and support for entrepreneurship, including access to finance, business training, and simplified registration procedures.

<https://lex.uz/uz/>

As well as, ¹²⁰ShavkatMirziyoyev, the President of Uzbekistan, has been a vocal supporter of tourism development in the country and has made several statements about the importance of the tourism industry in driving economic growth and promoting the country's cultural heritage. Here are some sentences from ShavkatMirziyoyev about tourism:

"Tourism is one of the most important sectors in the global economy and has great potential for development in Uzbekistan. We need to create the conditions for a comfortable and safe stay of tourists in our country, and provide them with quality service."

"Tourism is one of the important sectors of the economy. It is necessary to further improve this network, effectively using the existing opportunities, which takes time."

¹²⁰The President of Republic of Uzbekistan

"Tourism tomorrow's economy of our country and if we say that we will create jobs at the expense of tourism, we need to create conditions for tourists, not impose conditions".

These statements about tourism reflect the government's commitment to promoting sustainable tourism development in Uzbekistan, and to leveraging the country's cultural heritage and natural beauty to attract more visitors to the country.

2.METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection

The data for this study was collected from various sources. The primary source of data was the official websites of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan. These websites provided information about the hotels' amenities, room rates, location, and services. Additionally, data was collected from online travel agencies, such as Booking.com and TripAdvisor, which provided information on guest reviews, ratings, and bookings. The data collection process involved a comprehensive search of the official websites of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan. This search was conducted using various search engines, including Google and Yandex. The search terms used included "boutique hotels in Uzbekistan". The search was conducted in both English and Uzbek languages to ensure that all relevant information was collected. Once the official websites were identified, the data was extracted using a web scraping tool. The tool enabled the extraction of data such as hotel names, addresses, amenities, room rates, and services.

2.2 Data analysis

The data collected for this study were analysed using various statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics, competitive and consumer behaviour analyses. The content analysis for this study was determined by the number of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan. According to the Uzbekistan Tourism Board, there are approximately 50 boutique hotels in the country. Therefore, data was collected from all 50 hotels to ensure that the study was comprehensive and representative of the boutique hotel industry in Uzbekistan.

3. ANALYSIS AND COMMENTARY

3.1 The Identity Crisis of Boutique Hotels in Uzbekistan

Uzbekistan, a country with a rich history and cultural heritage, has recently seen a rise in the number of boutique hotels. These hotels are meant to offer a unique and intimate experience for travellers, but the design quality of these establishments has come under scrutiny. Despite the exterior facades of many boutique hotels in Uzbekistan appearing to be in line with the concept, their

interiors are often found to be more akin to modern hotels. This discrepancy points to a larger issue in the design and execution of boutique hotels in the country. The defining characteristic of boutique hotels is their distinctiveness in terms of design, atmosphere, and services offered. They are meant to be a reflection of the local culture and history, providing guests with a memorable experience. In the context of Uzbekistan, this would imply a blend of the region's rich cultural heritage with modern amenities and comforts. However, the current trend in Uzbekistan's boutique hotel industry suggests a disparity between the hotels' exterior and interior design. While the facades might be adorned with traditional Uzbek architectural elements and decorations, the interiors often reveal a completely different story. This incongruity not only dilutes the essence of boutique hotels, but also leaves guests with a sense of unfulfilled expectations.

Pictures 2 and 3

Mirza boutique hotel in Tashkent

3.2 The Root Causes of the Design Dilemma

There could be several reasons behind the lack of cohesive design in Uzbekistan's boutique hotels. One possibility is the limited availability of skilled designers and architects who can create a seamless integration of traditional and modern elements. This shortage of talent may force hotel owners to opt for readily available modern designs despite their preference for a more authentic experience. Another contributing factor could be the lack of clear guidelines and regulations from relevant organizations on what constitutes a boutique hotel. Without a proper framework in place, hotel owners might be unsure about how to achieve a balanced design that caters to the expectations of their target market. Lastly, the cost factor cannot be ignored. The restoration and preservation of traditional architecture and art can be expensive, and hotel owners might choose to invest in more affordable, modern designs to keep their expenses in check.

3.3 Competitive Analysis

The boutique hotel market in Uzbekistan is still developing compared to the well-established boutique hotel scene in France. There are only a handful of boutique hotels in major Uzbek cities like Tashkent and Samarkand, while Paris alone has over 50 boutique hotels and hundreds more across France. The style and design of Uzbek boutique hotels also tend to incorporate more traditional Uzbek cultural elements with colourful mosaics, carpets and tapestries. They aim to give guests an authentic experience of traditional Uzbek craftsmanship and living. Boutique hotels in France employ a wider range of styles from ultra-modern minimalism to romantic chic to avant-garde whimsy. Some do reflect aspects of traditional French design.

3.3.1 French boutique hotels

Boutique hotels in France are known for their unique and stylish designs that often reflect the local culture, history, and architecture. These hotels are typically small in size, with no more than 100 rooms, and are often located in historic buildings such as mansions, chateaus, or townhouses.

One popular design trend in French boutique hotels is a blend of traditional and contemporary elements. For example, you might see classic French furnishings combined with modern artwork or sleek lighting fixtures. This fusion of old and new creates a sophisticated and eclectic atmosphere that appeals to travellers looking for a one-of-a-kind experience.

Another common design feature in French boutique hotels is the use of natural materials such as stone, wood, and marble. These materials are often incorporated into the hotel's architecture, such as exposed stone walls or wooden beams, and can

also be found in the hotel's decor, such as rustic wooden furniture or natural fiber rugs.

French boutique hotels also often feature luxurious amenities, such as plush bedding, high-end toiletries, and spa services. These amenities are designed to create a sense of indulgence and relaxation for guests, and to enhance the overall experience of staying in a boutique hotel.

Picture 4

La Maison Sur La Sorgue - Boutique Hotel in France

Picture 5

La Maison Sur La Sorgue - Boutique Hotel in France

3.4 Results

Boutique hotels in Uzbekistan that are not well-designed may fail to meet the expectations of guests and can result in negative reviews and a lack of repeat

business. Some of the potential results of a poorly designed boutique hotel in Uzbekistan could include:

1. Uncomfortable and outdated furnishings: If the hotel's furnishings are not well-designed or maintained, guests may find them uncomfortable or unappealing, which can lead to a negative experience and poor reviews.

2. Inefficient use of space: A poorly designed boutique hotel may have awkward layouts or inefficient use of space, which can make rooms feel cramped and unwelcoming.

3. Lack of attention to detail: Boutique hotels are expected to provide a high level of personalized service and attention to detail. If the hotel's design does not reflect this attention to detail, guests may feel that their needs are not being met.

4. Inconsistent design: A boutique hotel should have a cohesive and consistent design throughout the property. If the design is inconsistent or disjointed, it can create a confusing and unappealing atmosphere for guests.

Overall, semi-designed boutique hotel in Uzbekistan can result in a negative experience for guests and can harm the hotel's reputation and business. It is essential for boutique hotels to invest in well-designed and maintained spaces to provide a high-quality experience for their guests.

4. INCREASING NUMBER OF BOUTIQUE HOTELS IN UZBEKISTAN

4.1 Why do we increase quantity of boutique hotels?

Firstly, Tourism growth. Uzbekistan's tourism industry has been growing rapidly in recent years, with over 6 million tourists visiting in 2018. Boutique hotels cater to higher-spending tourists interested in unique experiences. Attracting more of these tourists could help sustain tourism growth. Secondly, Promotion of cultural heritage. Boutique hotels in Uzbekistan highlight traditional Uzbek architecture, design, arts and crafts. Increasing their numbers can help support and promote these cultural elements of Uzbek heritage. They also give tourists a chance to experience them in an authentic way. Thirdly, Higher spending visitors. Boutique hotel guests tend to be more affluent, independent travellers willing to spend more on high quality experiences. Catering to these audiences can increase overall visitor spending in Uzbekistan's tourism economy. Lastly, Global interest. Boutique hotels have become popular around the world, especially among Western travellers. Developing more boutique hotels in Uzbekistan would put it on the map for global boutique travel lovers and help establish a unique selling point. Uzbekistan could become a new hub for stylish Central Asian boutique hotel experiences.

4.2 Minfiza Boutique hotel in Bukhara

Although many boutique hotels in Uzbekistan are slightly different in design from real boutique hotels. However, boutique hotels located in Bukhara meet the standards of real boutique hotels, and one of them is Minfiza, which combines the architecture, traditional materials, design and paying attention to every detail, you can see the hotel as a reflection of Uzbek culture. The hotel is located in the historical part of Bukhara - in the old city next to the EshoniPir Madrasah (16-19 centuries) and a 5-minute walk from the famous Lyabi Hauz architectural ensemble. Such a good location provides close proximity to most of the ancient monuments. By choosing the Minzifa Hotel, you will be convinced that being a guest can be just as good as being at home! Minzifa is distinguished by a unique combination of oriental elegance and home comfort. The hotel is situated in a traditional-style building with a central courtyard and offers comfortable rooms with traditional decor and modern amenities such as air conditioning, free Wi-Fi, and en-suite bathrooms. The hotel's restaurant serves a variety of Uzbek and international dishes, and there is also a bar where guests can enjoy a range of drinks. The hotel staff is reported to be friendly and helpful, and the hotel offers a range of services, including airport transfers, laundry, and tour arrangements.

Picture 6

Picture 7

Minfiza boutique hotel in Bukhara

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

To realize the original look and meaning of boutique hotel in Uzbekistan, there are several steps that can be taken.

1. Focus on unique local architecture and design. Boutique hotels are all about unique experiences and local flavour. Uzbekistan has a rich architectural heritage, including influences from Persian, Islamic and Soviet era styles. New boutique hotels should incorporate traditional Uzbek architectural elements like arched doorways, intricate tilework, and beautiful courtyards. They can also use local textiles, crafts and furnishings to enhance the unique ambiance.

2. Adapt historic buildings. Another option is to convert existing historic buildings like merchant houses, mansions or factories into boutique hotels. This allows for preservation of heritage architecture while giving the buildings a new lease of life. Many successful boutique hotels around the world have been adapted from historic buildings. However, the conversion needs to be done sensitively to maintain the character of the building.

3. Market to independent sophisticated travellers. Boutique hotels appeal primarily to experienced independent travellers looking for unique places to stay. Hotel marketers in Uzbekistan should target these travellers through media like travel blogs, influencer outreach, and partnerships with specialized tour operators. They need to convey the experiential nature of a stay at the boutique property. Those are some suggestions for spurring the growth of a vibrant boutique hotel sector in Uzbekistan that showcases the country's heritage while catering to

upmarket travellers seeking unique experiences. With its architectural legacy and potential for authentic luxury tourism, Uzbekistan has all the ingredients to develop a successful boutique hotel industry.

5.1 General recommendation for creating cultural atmosphere in boutique hotels in Uzbekistan

Creating a cultural atmosphere in boutique hotels in Uzbekistan involves incorporating elements of the local culture, history, and traditions into the hotel's design, decor, and amenities. Firstly, incorporate traditional design elements: Boutique hotels in Uzbekistan can incorporate traditional design elements such as ornate tilework, colourful fabrics, and intricate woodwork into their decor. These elements can be used in furniture, lighting, artwork, and accessories to create a unique and authentic atmosphere that reflects the local culture. Secondly, use local materials: Using local materials such as wood, stone, and clay can help create a sense of place and connect the hotel to the local environment. For example, a hotel in Bukhara could use local adobe bricks in its construction or incorporate traditional Uzbek textiles into its decor. Thirdly, feature local artwork: Displaying artwork by local artists can help guests connect with the local culture and appreciate the art and traditions of Uzbekistan. This could include traditional textiles, ceramics, or paintings. Fourthly, offer local cuisine: Boutique hotels in Uzbekistan can feature local cuisine in their restaurants, cafes, or bars. Offering traditional Uzbek dishes such as pilaf, shashlik, or somsa can provide guests with a taste of local flavour and help them connect with the local culture. Lastly, provide cultural activities: Offering cultural activities such as traditional music and dance performances, cooking classes, or guided tours can help guests immerse themselves in the local culture and traditions. This can also provide an opportunity for guests to learn more about Uzbekistan's history and heritage. Total, creating a cultural atmosphere in boutique hotels in Uzbekistan involves incorporating local elements into the hotel's design, decor, cuisine, and activities. This can help guests connect with the local culture and traditions and create a unique and memorable experience.

Picture 8

Uzbek culture- Folk Crafts in Uzbekistan

6. CONCLUSION

Uzbekistan is seeing a growing trend of boutique hotels that offer a unique and personalized experience to guests. These boutique hotels are providing high-quality design, amenities, and services in charming properties. They should also incorporate local Uzbek design elements and cultural touches into their spaces in an authentic way. Well-designed, culturally immersed boutique hotels will help promote tourism to Uzbekistan and bring more visitors to experience the history, heritage, and hospitality of the country. It also means investing in high-quality materials and furnishings to create a luxurious and comfortable experience for guests. In addition, by improving the quality and design of boutique hotels in Uzbekistan, we can help more tourists experience Uzbek culture and thereby increase the flow of tourists. Our boutique hotels in Bukhara will further strengthen the quality of boutique hotels that meet the standards of hotels in countries such as France, one of the world's leading countries.

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